

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
Institute of Engineering & Technology
Mukka, Mangalore

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AISHWARYA M BETTIN**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC001** has completed his/her minor project on “ *Piezo-Electric Energy Harvesting and Management in WSN* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AKSHAR KUMAR SHETTY

bearing USN 1SU20EC002 has completed his/her minor project on “*A Laser Scanning Methodology for 3D Printing*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMARGEETH**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC003** has completed his/her minor project on “**DIY Segway**” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms GAGAN V

bearing USN 1SU20EC004 has completed his/her minor project on “*SmartSur: Smart Video SURveillance System*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

Dean, SUIET

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GANESH VISHWANATH BHAT**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC005** has completed his/her minor project on “ *Dynamic Car Parking Negotiation And Guidance Using An Agent-Based Platform* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HIMASHREE PRIYA M**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC006** has completed his/her minor project on “ *Monitor and Control of Greenhouse Environment* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JOSEPH N K**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC007** has completed his/her minor project on “**VHDL Modelling of Glue Logic of 1553b Interface Board**” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MALCOM D SOUZA**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC008** has completed his/her minor project on “*Weather Station*”
in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for
the academic year 2020 - 21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms S L ROHITHKUMAR

bearing USN 1SU20EC009 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Blind navigation system using RFID for indoor environments* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAYEEDA SHAFaq ALAM**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC010** has completed his/her minor project on “ *Cell Phone Operated Robot* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHIVAPRIYA MAHESH KORI**

bearing USN 1SU20EC011 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Traffic Light Control System* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SRUJAN ACHAR**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC012** has completed his/her minor project on “*A Bi-directional Visitors Counter*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SWASTHIK NAYAK**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC013** has completed his/her minor project on “***Bomb Detection Robotics Using Embedded Controller***” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDULLAH AKBAR P**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC014** has completed his/her minor project on “*Telephone Router*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHAY Y RAO

bearing USN 1SU20EC015 has completed his/her minor project on “*Intelligent Alcohol Detection System for CAR*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHIN RAI B**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC016** has completed his/her minor project on “ **Centrally Controlled Multichannel Token Display** ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKASH V NAIR**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC017** has completed his/her minor project on “*Microcontroller Based Cellular Voting Machine*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANAND ASHOK YADAHALLI

bearing USN 1SU20EC018 has completed his/her minor project on “*Two ways Wireless Anti Theft Alarm system for Two Wheeler*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANIRUDH S

bearing USN 1SU20EC019 has completed his/her minor project on “*Micro Controller based Security System using Sonar*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANVEEKSH M S SINGH

bearing USN 1SU20EC020 has completed his/her minor project on “*Frequency Counter*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AVINASH K R

bearing USN 1SU20EC021 has completed his/her minor project on “*Micro Controller based Burner Automation*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BIBITHA V R**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC022** has completed his/her minor project on “**Device Controlling Using TAPI**” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHETAN SURESH SHET**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC023** has completed his/her minor project on “ *Telephone Triggered Switches* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **CHIDANAND BABU KALLIBADDI**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC024** has completed his/her minor project on “***SPEEDES Qheap***” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DIVIN K R**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC025** has completed his/her minor project on “ **Wireless Motor Control System** ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms FARA ROSHAN

bearing USN 1SU20EC026 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Card Based Security System* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms GAUTHAM S B

bearing USN 1SU20EC027 has completed his/her minor project on “ *Microcontroller Based Barcode Decoder* ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **K SWATHI RAO**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC028** has completed his/her minor project on “ ***Intelligent Fire Sprinkler System*** ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KARTHIK D**

bearing USN 1SU20EC029 has completed his/her minor project on “ ***GSM Path Planning For Blind Person Using Ultrasonic*** ” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KARTHIK SAINATH SHETTY**

bearing **USN 1SU20EC030** has completed his/her minor project on “*Infrared Remote Control*” in the first Semester of the Electronics & Communication Engineering programme for the academic year 2020 - 21.

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